

European Tourism Data Space

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D6.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan

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List of Acronyms

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BtoB	Business to Business
BtoG	Business to Government
DG	Directorate General
DSSC	Data Spaces Support Centre
DMOs	Destination Management Organization
D&CP	Dissemination and Communication Plan
ETDS	European Tourism Data Space
EU	European Union
HaDEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
IDSA	International Data Space Association
KER	Key Exploitable Results
KoM	Kick Off Meeting
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
M	Month
SMEs	Small and medium-sized enterprises
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

This document is a deliverable submitted in the frame of the DEPLOYTOUR project, co-funded by the European Commission.

The DEPLOYTOUR - Deployment of a trusted and secure Common European Tourism Data Space- aims at creating a unified European Tourism Data Space. By facilitating sovereign data-sharing across borders and between public and private sectors, the project will help enhance efficiency in operational processes, enable new services to emerge, improving the user experience, stimulating innovation (including access to data for AI), and contribute to the digital and sustainable transition of the tourism sector.

The Dissemination and Communication Plan (D&CP) outlines **the strategy and guidelines for effectively implementing communication and dissemination activities** over the project's three-year duration. This work package (WP) is a **transversal work package** designed to ensure optimal **outreach and engagement towards key target groups**, including the data and tourism communities and the general public. WP6 seeks to **raise awareness of the benefits of the European Tourism Data Space (ETDS)** for all stakeholders.

EONA-X, as the lead partner of WP6, is responsible for designing and executing the D&CP, with strong support from DISSET and AnySolution, with the **active involvement of all consortium partners**. The partners will facilitate local communication activities and contribute as ambassadors to disseminating project outcomes.

The D&CP is a **strategic roadmap for ensuring timely and impactful project communication and dissemination activities**. It follows the communication requirements of the European Digital Europe Programme.

WP6 encompasses a range of tasks, including **managing the project's internal and external communication flow**, creating a distinctive brand and **visual identity** for easy recognition, and disseminating the project's progress and results throughout its lifecycle. WP6 collaborates closely with all project work packages and is key in **promoting and highlighting the project's five real-life use case pilots**.

This document includes detailed information on **key messages, communication tools and channels, target audiences, planned activities, and their timelines, monitoring tools, and indicators**.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the Document

This deliverable is the plan to fulfil the following objectives:

- **Objective 5:** Implement an efficient dissemination, communication, and exploitation strategy.
- **Objective 5.1:** To reach the tourism and data communities and reach the overall project’s objectives of ensuring a good understanding of the benefits of the ETDS and to facilitate the exploitation of the project’s results.
- **Objective 5.2:** Elaboration of business models centred on the data and the digital applications that will conform to the ETDS to demonstrate the benefit of inter-organizational cooperation. WP6 will contribute to this objective by promoting the selected business model and assisting WP3 Governance in its development.

This document outlines the activities planned for dissemination and communication within the DEPLOYTOUR project, serving as a comprehensive guideline for all partners.

It provides a **detailed roadmap** for planning and executing these activities, specifying what will be done, when, and how. The aim is to **ensure project partners effectively communicate key messages and outcomes to the distinct target audiences identified for the project but also clearly understand and be aligned internally on the communication about the project.**

A clear and impactful strategy has been developed to enhance the project’s visibility and outreach. This includes organizing events such as **training and webinars, creating targeted communication materials, and tailoring messages** for specific audience groups. A dedicated **website** will be launched earlier than initially planned, going live by Month 3 (M3), instead of Month 6 (M6), and maintained for five years beyond the project’s conclusion. DEPLOYTOUR’s presence on **LinkedIn and X** (formerly Twitter) will further facilitate accessibility for targeted audiences. These platforms will also serve as channels for bi-directional communication, enabling feedback from the user community, citizens, and organizations involved in data-related organizations.

DEPLOYTOUR aims to **engage connections through conferences, webinars, workshops, online webinars, project website, articles, press releases, newsletters, blogs, social media and events**, involving tourism and data stakeholders to join the discussion and contribute to the initiative’s development, ensuring its sustainability. Therefore it will also put effort into **generating synergies** with other data spaces, data spaces initiatives, European projects as well as other communities relevant for the project. WP6 and WP5 (Synergies, recommendations, connections) will work closely.

The exploitation strategy and training (task 6.3) are aimed at supporting the knowledge about the solutions developed in the project. The project’s Key Exploitable Results (KERs) will be available in a matchmaking platform linked to other Data Spaces. Adding to that, an online training programme with content addressing different target groups will be created involving experts from the consortium and beyond, as well as for peer learning to broaden the European ecosystem of data providers and users of data spaces.

The plan will be regularly updated to remain relevant and adaptable to evolving needs. Results will be documented in **periodic reports**, due in Months 12, 24, and 36. Monthly meetings will also be held to review ongoing activities and track Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), ensuring that the project stays aligned with its goals and makes adjustments as needed.

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EONA-X is the leader of WP6, and this WP is divided into the following tasks:

- T6.1. Dissemination and communication strategy
- T6.2. Outreach and awareness activities
- T6.3. Exploitation strategy and training

All the project’s partners are involved in this Work Package.

1.2 Structure of the Document

The deliverable is structured in 4 sections:

- Sections 1 and 2 set the basis of the document, including introductory information and an overview of the targeted stakeholders. Section 2 outlines the DEPLOYTOUR key messages designed to align with stakeholders' interests and expectations.
- Section 3 defines the activities and plans to be implemented in communication and dissemination.
- Section 4 introduces important synergy actions to be considered linked with WP5.
- Section 5 sets the conclusion.

The sections are organized into various subsections to provide a clear and logical outline of the activities described in this document.

For the Communication and Dissemination section, which is the biggest section, the main parts are:

- Dissemination and Communication Procedures to ensure smooth and efficient internal and external communication.
- Project's visual identity, where the main features of DEPLOYTOUR's visual identity are defined, together with the EU emblem, disclaimer and templates.
- Communication Tools and Channels: presentation of the website and the social media platforms that will be heavily used to promote the project's outcomes and the newsletters release strategy.
- Dissemination activities: this part incorporates a diverse mix of tools to maximise outreach and stakeholder engagement, such as webinars, in-person events, press releases, articles and branded materials.
- Monitoring and evaluation of communication and dissemination: This last section is about the key performance indicators (KPIs) that will track progress and the means to follow up on the advancement in the fulfilment of the KPIs.

The Networking and synergies section introduces the actions that will be undertaken to engage with the identified organizations, such as data spaces communities, to build a strong ecosystem of stakeholders.

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2 Overall Approach

2.1 Overall Methodology and Means

The plan for implementing the communication and dissemination activities must align with the overall methodology of the project (as established in the Grant Agreement) and the WP6 **main objective, which is to effectively communicate the benefits of the common European tourism data space, as well as the specific results and outcomes of the project to a wide range of stakeholders**, including policymakers, industry leaders, and the general public.

DEPLOYTOUR will use different supports to communicate and disseminate the project's results and outcomes. Different channels have been identified, such as:

- The project website,
- Online webinars,
- Conferences and events,
- Articles,
- Press releases,
- Posts on social media,
- Newsletters,
- Blog articles.

Leaflets, roll-ups, notebooks, pens, infographics, and short video-clips will serve as additional tools to enhance communication efforts.

EONA-X, as the lead beneficiary of WP6, along with DISSET, has a **dedicated budget** to organize events, host online webinars, participate in conferences, and develop a comprehensive training program. This budget also supports some subcontracting and event organization services, ensuring effective training sessions for project members and promoting the project externally.

Four phases will guide the implementation of the activities described in WP6 throughout the project:

- **Phase I - Dissemination and communication strategy (M1-M2)**, in which the strategy to ensure the achievement of the outcomes will be defined, together with the first set of communication and dissemination activities.
- **Phase II - Outreach and awareness activities (M1- M36)**, in which all activities described in this document and the Grant Agreement will be implemented, ensuring the involvement of stakeholders and reaching all target groups, as well as generating synergies and complementarities with the all the stakeholders, relevant projects and initiatives
- **Phase III - Exploitation strategy and training (M12 - M36)**, in which the project outcomes and results will be available, and online training will be created.
- **Phase IV – post-project sustainability (M36 – five years after the project completion)**: project legacy and dissemination of key and wider impacts. It is expected that the project's results will be scalable.

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2.2 Target Groups

DEPLOYTOUR actively involves different stakeholder groups by utilizing various channels to communicate and disseminate DEPLOYTOUR project content.

Communication and dissemination are also carried out through the networks of project partners and their involvement in other European projects (such as deployEMDS, D3hub, and CyclOps) as well as their connections to various networks and platforms (including IDSA, GAIA-X, DSSC, Fiware, and UN tourism). To maximise the impact of these efforts, all project partners are committed to engaging relevant stakeholders throughout the project's lifecycle and leveraging their extensive networking capabilities.

The main target groups identified by DEPLOYTOUR cover a wide range of groups such as:

DEPLOYTOUR Target Groups	Example of Stakeholders	Main Messages to raise awareness and attract target groups	Channels
EU decision makers, local and public authorities	European Commission DG Grow DG Connect HaDEA National ministries National agencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The creation of a roadmap and design principles towards the EU Data Space: deploying a robust technical infrastructure and governance mechanisms, aligning with the DSSC and data spaces frameworks and leveraging the insights gained from the preparatory actions. • Demonstrating the potential value proposition of using data spaces in a specific sector: data sovereignty, usage control, better discovery and flow of quality data, easier BtoB or BtoG collaboration... • Increasing the tourism sector's competitiveness by enabling new types of services and giving access to quality data for AI uses. • Deployment of innovative services and applications through 5 real-life thematic pilots. • Demonstrating cross-border data sharing, having some use case pilots deployed between several countries. 	Events Reports Public Deliverables Press releases Social Media Website
Business and operational stakeholders	Data users Data providers From the tourism sector (SMEs, big companies)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deploying a technical infrastructure and governance mechanisms, ensuring secure and controlled access to data relevant for tourism stakeholders: providing the tools and governance mechanisms for trusted environments to mitigate current risks in data sharing and optimizing processes and developing. • Data accessibility through 5 pilots: facilitate access to a large choice of useful and reliable data. • Best practices from real-world data space implementations: feedback to further evolving common frameworks and standards, based on 5 pilots across Europe and networking potential for data sharing, interoperability and upscaling of 	Public Deliverables Newsletter Press releases Events Articles Social Media Website

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DEPLOYTOUR Target Groups	Example of Stakeholders	Main Messages to raise awareness and attract target groups	Channels
		<p>project results for exploitation, transfer of knowledge.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ecosystem development: Collaboration with both public and private actors in European countries. • Innovative services and applications supporting sustainable actions for tourism through technologies and understanding and learning from the pain points and opportunities developed in the project's use cases. Project outputs will also refer to the Tourism Transition Pathway, to support the strategy of digital and sustainable transition. 	
<p>Functional and technology stakeholders (implementation enablers)</p> <p>Data Spaces communities</p>	<p>Consulting companies</p> <p>Tech companies</p> <p>Tech providers (not specifically in the tourism sector)</p> <p>IDSA, GAIA-X, DSSC, FIWARE</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deploying a common technical infrastructure and governance mechanisms: deployment of a common technical infrastructure, to meet the requirements of use cases and align with the emerging European data spaces technical framework, DSSC, SIMPL, and the preparatory actions. • Feedback on project progress: providing feedback on how these frameworks actually "work" (or not) in real-world applications and their limits. • Interoperability: the objective is to reach KPIs that include ensuring the interoperability of the common technical infrastructure. • Data accessibility through 5 pilots: facilitate access to a large choice of useful and reliable data. • Opportunity to participate in data space technical groups or to stay informed about the project's progress, for example by attending public webinars on the use case pilots or by participating in the DSSC groups. 	<p>Webinar</p> <p>Event</p> <p>Newsletter</p> <p>Article</p> <p>Social Media</p> <p>Website</p>

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DEPLOYTOUR Target Groups	Example of Stakeholders	Main Messages to raise awareness and attract target groups	Channels
General public and media		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive impact on tourism experiences: DEPLOYTOUR contributes to the development of innovative services and applications, demonstrating their potential through real-life use cases. • Discovering data spaces: DEPLOYTOUR facilitates access to data, focusing on creating a secure, sovereignty-conscious space for data sharing with specific policies designed by data owners. This approach addresses concerns around data sharing, particularly in BtoB and BtoG contexts. By enabling the creation of large data ecosystems, the project supports the advancement of smart tourism strategies at european level. • Collaborative ecosystem: DEPLOYTOUR is committed to fostering collaboration among data providers and users, encompassing public and private actors across European countries but also between large groups and SMEs. This cooperative approach is key in shaping the future of a resilient data-driven tourism sector. 	Press Release Press kit Webinar Social Media Website

Table 1 DEPLOYTOUR Target Groups

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3 Communication and Dissemination Means and Plan

The project's Dissemination and Communication Plan aims to inform relevant stakeholders and communities about the **activities, results, and achievements carried out within the project**. The strategy also aims at generating **interest** and facilitating the **engagement** of key stakeholders, generating a community of interest around data-collaboration in Tourism.

The plan, which will be periodically updated in line with lessons learned and project progress, includes an articulation of the project's **visual identity** (in line with the guidelines of the European Commission), the identification of **target audiences**, a set of **key messages**, appropriate dissemination **tools and channels** to reach the selected target groups, and a **performance monitoring framework**.

Dissemination, communication, and engagement activities will follow the guidelines developed at this early stage of the project. The measurable outcomes are the release of the **project's website, posts on LinkedIn**, the number of **events** organized/participated in, online **webinars**, and at least one contribution to dataspace strategic documents. Project presentations and demonstrations are planned at key European and international congresses and events, as well as during an **annual high-level event in Brussels** organized by DEPLOYTOUR itself.

3.1 Dissemination and Communication Procedures

Effective project communication is essential for its success. While project activities and outcomes must be promoted through information campaigns targeting various audiences, including the media and the general public, **it is equally important that the initial information and results from project activities are communicated effectively among partners**. This ensures that the consortium clearly understands overall progress, helps identify potential synergies, and uncovers unexpected findings that could contribute to the project's success.

All communication channels and tools created for the project not only address its external environment but also focus on strengthening the partnership among its members. The leader of Dissemination and Communication, EONA-X is responsible for supporting partners and work package activities in their communication and dissemination needs, as well as ensuring adequate communication and broad dissemination of all project activities of the consortium.

To ensure smooth and efficient internal and external communication some processes have been set up and will be adapted throughout the project:

- **Coordination meetings** with the main WP6 partners will be held as needed. During periods of high activity, these meetings may occur weekly, while at other times, they may be scheduled less frequently.
- **Monthly Meetings with all WP6 involved partners to give reports** on past actions and heads-up on coming events and accepted actions.
- **A shared document for upcoming events**, which partners can update monthly to organise themselves, use appropriate materials for presenting DEPLOYTOUR, and share content for the WP6 team to communicate.
- **Monthly email reminders** for partners to complete the Communication and Dissemination Monitoring tool.
- **Regular updates to the DEPLOYTOUR website and posts on social media** accounts with project news, partner progress, achievements, and other relevant

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updates to keep partners informed and encourage them to follow, subscribe, and engage.

- Issuing the **internal newsletter** with partners and activity updates, events, and other relevant news: 4 times per year (every quarter).
- Issuing the **external newsletter** with updates for relevant stakeholders and individuals who subscribe through the website: 4 times per year (every quarter, using LinkedIn newsletter option for example to engage directly with our community)..

To support partners in their communication and dissemination efforts, a **Communication Guidelines document** will be shared. This document will serve as a reference throughout the project, outlining the European communication requirements, social media tags, hashtags, and visual identity to be used. It also includes available documents and templates to assist partners with their communication activities and reporting tasks along with best practices, such as including [DEPLOYTOUR] in the subject line of emails for clarity when contacting partners about DEPLOYTOUR.

A **shared folder** is currently available as a repository for documents, logos, presentations, templates, and meeting minutes, accessible to DEPLOYTOUR partners. This will soon be replaced by an intranet accessible through the project website.

3.1.1 Visual Identity

The project's visual identity serves as the backbone of all its initiatives and communications, it's the unifying element that ties together everything from promotional materials to internal communications. A strong visual identity provides a consistent and memorable impression, reinforcing the project's brand and fostering a sense of cohesion among its stakeholders. DEPLOYTOUR's logo and palette have been conceived to make the project more recognizable and memorable. Consistent branding across all communication channels helps to build a strong identity.

The visual identity represents the whole project. DEPLOYTOUR's visual identity is consistent and easy to recognize. Its logo is represented by concentric coloured circles that are open or complete each other. This dynamic, circular icon symbolizes four key concepts:

1. **Data Sharing:** The concentric circles within the icon represent a data disk, symbolizing the sharing of information.
2. **Tourism:** The circular shape is linked to the sun, often associated with the tourism industry.
3. **Security:** The fingerprint-like pattern within the icon represents the security and confidentiality of data.
4. **Integration:** The icon seamlessly integrates the letter "O" from the DEPLOYTOUR brand, highlighting its central role in the project

Therefore, these are the details of the creation process. DEPLOYTOUR's visual identity was created considering the following:

- Data disc
- sun/tourism
- fingerprint
- letter "o"

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Figure 1 DEPLOYTOUR's logo creative concept

Corporate colours

Blue is widely associated with the European Union due to its prominence in the EU flag. Using blue in the EU flag and branding has contributed to its recognition and association with European values and ideals. It is also often associated with 'trust', which is a capital element in data sharing.

The corporate colour is Pantone 541 C, and Pantone 7461 C to generate contrast. In addition, the other colours that make up the isotype are used: Pantone 638 C, Pantone 382 C, Pantone 1495 C and Pantone 485 C. Occasionally, Pantone 539 C can be used for backgrounds. Grey at 70% can also be incorporated for corporate text.

The use of a wide range of colours, accompanied by the more corporate blue, indicates the cross-border desire of the project to incorporate a diversity of partners from different origins and countries.

Figure 2 Description of DEPLOYTOUR's corporate colours

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Brand typography

The corporate typeface is the Arial family. Usually, only the Black and Regular versions are used.

3.1.2 Logo

The logo will be used in all internal and external communications and dissemination activities (project website, presentations, flyers, press releases etc...) to help enhance brand continuity and raise awareness.

Three logo variants have been chosen: the original one in colour, plus blue and white:

Figure 3 Description of DEPLOYTOUR's corporate colours

To prevent incorrect use of the logo, the following instructions have been communicated:

1. Do not change the typography
2. Do not deform the brand
3. Do not use gradients
4. Do not change the colours
5. Do not vary the proportions of your elements
6. Do not change the spacing
7. Do not move elements
8. Do not apply shading

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Figure 4 Wrong uses of DEPLOYTOUR’s logo

3.1.3 EU Emblem

All the DEPLOYTOUR communication and engagement materials will follow the requirements set out by the European Commission and will include the EU flag and the funding statement.

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Co-funded by the European Union

Co-funded by the European Union

Co-funded by the European Union

Figure 5 EU emblem

3.1.4 Disclaimer

Partners are aware that all public communication and dissemination materials must incorporate the following disclaimer and be translated into different languages if necessary:

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3.1.5 Templates

DEPLOYTOUR will be presented at a number of different events, conferences, workshops as well as other occasions to disseminate project developments and results. For this reason, a distinctive, tridimensional pattern in a vibrant color palette has been designed for both these templates and the website, giving the project a strong identity linked to data. This visual element, combined with the European Union's corporate blue, creates a powerful and memorable brand image.

Figure 6 Cover of DEPLOYTOUR'S PPT template

Figure 7 Body of DEPLOYTOUR'S PPT template

All DEPLOYTOUR templates' designs are carefully aligned with the project's visual identity, respecting each of the elements defined to represent it.

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Call for proposals	Call ID	
Grant Agreement No.	101173388	Start date
Project duration	36 months	End date
		1 October 2024

Contact: projects@anysof.com
Website: www.deploytour.eu

Project consortium – Coordinator:			
Affiliate entity long name	AE – Short name	...	BEN – ...
Partner 2 long name	BEN – partner 2 short name	...	BEN – ...
...	BEN	BEN ...
...	BEN	BEN ...

DX.X Name of the Deliverable

Document Identification			
Status	Draft/Final (final once approved by HDDEA)	Due Date	
Version	0.1, 0.2, ... 3.0 (version 1.0 is to submit the final time to HDDEA)	Submission Date	

Related WP	WP1	Document Reference	WP1/01
Related Deliverable(s)	DX.X	Dissemination Level (*)	Public
Lead Partner	Name of the partner	Lead Author	Name of the person leading the partner
Contributors	Name of the partner	Reviewers	AnySol

Document name:	DX.X Name of the Deliverable	Page:	1 of 14
Reference:	DX.X Dissemination: BEN/PU Version: DX.X Status: Draft/Final		

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Document Information

List of Contributors	
Name	Partner

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0.1			Initial version
0.2			
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0.4			
0.5			

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Project Coordinator	AnySol	

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Figure 8 DEPLOYTOUR’s Deliverable cover (LEFT) and body (RIGHT)

3.2 Communication Tools and Channels

3.2.1 Website

The DEPLOYTOUR website serves as a central point for information, collaboration and dissemination of results. This online platform allows project partners and the wider community to stay informed and actively participate in DEPLOYTOUR’s activities, such as conferences, workshops or events. The website shares information about the project progress and results, providing access to documents and reports.

Social media is also integrated into the web strategy, allowing to extend its reach and connect with a wider audience. Through platforms such as X, LinkedIn and YouTube, it can share relevant content, interact with the community and promote news, events and activities.

Although still in production, this is the structure of the website:

- The Project:** the reader can understand the objectives of the project, get to know the consortium and subscribe to the newsletter
- Use Case Pilots:** it allows people to understand that there are 5 pilots in the project.
- Events:** it is dedicated to events in which the DEPLOYTOUR project participates and to future events planned as a tool for promotion, networking, learning and validation, helping to drive the project forward and establish meaningful connections in its ecosystem.
- Resources:** it includes all the news sections created by the consortium: blog, newsletters, press releases, scientific publications, workshops, public deliverables...

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5. **Contact:** the contact information of the project coordinator.
6. **Log in:** This section will be for the private use of the partners where they will be able to access private project information. This is a key point for sharing and accessing information privately. The information will be organised in folders so that access is limited to the appropriate partners.
7. **Privacy/cookies policies:** the privacy policy document informs users of how the personal data is protected, collected and used on the website, including the handling of cookies and other trackers. On the other hand, cookies collect data about users' actions on the website.

Figure 9 DEPLOYTOUR's provisional landing page

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Figure 10 DEPLOYTOUR’s provisional landing page ‘Under construction’

Even though still in production, the web has already been completely designed, both in its mobile and desktop versions.

Figure 11 DEPLOYTOUR’s full web design

3.2.2 Social Media Channels

Social media has become one of the most effective tools for reaching and engaging a broad audience. While many social networks exist, fewer cater specifically to professional or expert communities. The most widely used platforms for these audiences are LinkedIn and X (formerly Twitter). Given the trend towards more visual content, YouTube has also been included, offering multilingual communication through its translation features and the ability to showcase project developments, such as progress in the use cases.

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A tool to effectively manage DEPLOYTOUR accounts, enabling a streamlined review process, detailed analytics of each social media and post planning, is currently under consideration.

To maximize visibility and impact, **all partners are encouraged to post content on their social media accounts and share posts from the official project accounts** (@DEPLOYTOUR-Deployment European Tourism Data Space). When partners share project-related content, they are required to tag the project, @European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA), @the European Commission, @AnySolution as project coordinator as well as the project-specific hashtags. This approach boosts traffic to both the project and partner networks.

Project-relevant **hashtags** have also been created and shared with the partners. Some examples are: #DEPLOYTOUR; #dataspaces; #datasharing; #tourismdataspace; #EUtourism. Project-specific hashtags, shared with partners, are an essential part of the strategy. For example, using relevant hashtags helps target audiences discover DEPLOYTOUR and its outputs. By leveraging hashtags, we can:

- Engage and influence key communities with our messages.
- Expand the project’s reach and attract individuals interested in data spaces.
- Establish collaborative relationships and share resources and ideas with other projects.

3.2.2.1 LinkedIn

DEPLOYTOUR leverages LinkedIn to connect with key target groups, share project updates, and promote events and activities where the project is showcased. This platform serves as a hub for disseminating project results, activities, and documents, while also attracting a broader audience and fostering a strong community through idea exchange.

The DEPLOYTOUR LinkedIn account **builds on the existing community established by the preparatory actions, DATES**. This strategic decision allows DEPLOYTOUR to benefit from DATES’ established network. As of Month 1 of DEPLOYTOUR, the LinkedIn account already had 1324 followers.

During the Kick-off Meeting, a dedicated session was held to guide partners on creating LinkedIn posts about DEPLOYTOUR. This included best practices, such as recommended hashtags, tagging relevant organizations, adhering to the project's visual identity, and incorporating logos. To streamline content creation for partners, **a custom Canva template was provided**, making it easier for them to create and share posts about DEPLOYTOUR on LinkedIn.

Figure 12 DEPLOYTOUR’s canva template

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All partners' social media tags are compiled in a shared Excel file, ensuring that LinkedIn profiles can be tagged to maximize the reach and impact of posts.

Figure 13 DEPLOYTOUR's LinkedIn account: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/deploytour>

3.2.3 X

DEPLOYTOUR's X account is also built on the DATES account, starting with 240 followers.

X enables quick, direct communication with target groups, sharing project news, events, and updates. Its short message format is ideal for delivering specific, targeted content. To enhance engagement and reach, all partners are encouraged to retweet posts from their accounts, helping to expand the project's impact. It is important to notice that X is less widely used than LinkedIn.

Figure 14 DEPLOYTOUR's X account: <https://x.com/DEPLOYTOUR>

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3.2.3.1 YouTube

DEPLOYTOUR uses this channel to reach people interested in DEPLOYTOUR content by making available: online workshops, project presentations, webinars, case studies, etc.

Figure 15 DEPLOYTOUR’s YouTube account: <https://www.youtube.com/@DeploytourTourismDataspace>

3.2.4 Newsletter

Two different types of newsletters will be released

- **Internal Newsletter:** This newsletter aims to keep consortium partners informed about key updates, upcoming project milestones, and events, and will highlight internal achievements. It will be a brief and concise newsletter with project updates, important dates (meetings, deliverables), acknowledgements of the team’s work... The first internal newsletter release is planned for mid-December.
- **External Newsletter:** This newsletter will engage a broader audience and foster a community around the European Tourism Data Space. Subscriptions will be available via the project website and the LinkedIn newsletter feature. The first external newsletter will be shared in mid-December as well.

Both newsletters will be issued quarterly and will include updates on project activities, workshops, training materials, publications, reports, and other essential content.

3.3 Dissemination Activities

3.3.1 Dissemination supports

DEPLOYTOUR will employ various tools to share project outcomes and engage targeted stakeholders effectively.

- **Webinars:**
 - **Internal Webinars:** Six webinars will be organized for project members and invitees, starting with the first session in February. Five additional webinars will focus on use case progress, outcomes, and feedback.
 - **External Webinars:** Aimed at a broader audience, including DMOs, decision-makers, tourism professionals, journalists, and the general public. Each webinar will feature topic-specific experts to provide valuable insights and knowledge.
- **In-Person Events:**

In-person events are pivotal for engaging stakeholders and amplifying project visibility. DEPLOYTOUR’s event strategy includes:

 - **A Kick-Off Event and a Final Event.**

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- Three **high-level events** in Brussels, aligned with three use case-specific events.
- Five additional **destination-based events** (one per pilot location). Participation in key tourism and data-related events will also ensure networking opportunities, community engagement, and visibility.
- DEPLOYTOUR partners will actively participate in major data and tourism events, leveraging these opportunities to promote the project whenever feasible.
- **Coordination for Events:**
 - A shared table will help partners document and coordinate event attendance. This ensures collaboration between attendees and allows WP6 to promote partner participation via social media and other channels.
 - Coordination among partners fosters synergy, ensuring impactful and unified representation at events.
- **Content Creation and Media Engagement**
- **Website Articles:** Regular updates, such as event summaries, deliverable publications, and use case pilot progress, will be published to drive website traffic and engage targeted audiences.
- **Press Releases:** Issued for significant DEPLOYTOUR milestones, such as the Kick-Off Meeting, high-level events, use case pilot launches, and the Final Event. These will be shared with local media to boost awareness and participation.

By leveraging a comprehensive mix of webinars, events, online content, and press coverage, DEPLOYTOUR aims to maximize its outreach and impact while fostering meaningful engagement across its target audiences.

3.3.2 Collaterals

Roller-ups: To reinforce the corporate image of the project and help spread the main ideas of DEPLOYTOUR, two roller-ups have been initially designed and launched at the KoM in Palma. One of them summarised the reasons for the project, while the second has the main information of the five pilot projects. They are to be used at physical events and meetings for eye-catching identification of the DEPLOYTOUR project. During the duration of the project, other roller-ups will be designed and produced to suit the needs that arise.

Figure 16 DEPLOYTOUR's roll-ups

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Notebooks: to be used at in-person events and meetings, to strengthen the corporate presence of the DEPLOYTOUR brand.

Figure 17 DEPLOYTOUR’s notebooks

Pens: also to be used at in-person events and meetings to strengthen the corporate presence of the DEPLOYTOUR brand.

Figure 18 DEPLOYTOUR’s pens

Folders: these are to be used at in-person events and meetings to strengthen the corporate presence of the DEPLOYTOUR brand.

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Figure 19 DEPLOYTOUR’s folders

ID cards: to be used at in-person events and meetings. The blue color strengthens the EU corporate brand.

Figure 20 DEPLOYTOUR’s ID cards

3.3.3 Videos

Over the 36-month duration of the project, some videos will be uploaded, including partner introductions, project overviews, and recorded webinars. Some of the videos will be publicly accessible, while others will remain for internal use, with the YouTube channel serving as a repository for this content.

These videos will showcase the project’s progress and results, offering visibility to the implementation and outcomes of the pilots while promoting the project’s overall achievements.

3.4 Monitoring and Evaluation of Communication and Dissemination

3.4.1 KPI’s

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are essential benchmarks for achieving project objectives. They enable continuous progress evaluation and allow for timely corrective actions if necessary. In the context of the DEPLOYTOUR Dissemination and Communication Plan, these KPIs encompass a range of metrics, including different tools and supports (LinkedIn, webinars, events, strategic document) and the volume of activity associated.

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The table below serves as a monitoring and evaluation tool for KPI progress throughout the project.

Tools/Channels	KPI	Target value			Current	Comments
		Year 1	Year 2	Year 3		
Communication tools & Channels	LinkedIn	Number of posts on LinkedIn			>1000	15
	Online Webinars	Number of online webinars			6	6 for the project members and invites: - Dataspace presentation - One per pilote - WP4 Regular webinars addressed to a wider audience (DMOs, decision makers, tourism professionals, journalists, general public...)
Events	Events	Number of events organised/participated			>30	11 Kick-off, Final events, 3 high level events in Brussels combine with 3 use case events + 5 in-person events throughout the duration of the project (1 per pilot destination) + participating in almost all event related to tourism and data
Publications	Strategic document	Contributions to dataspace strategic documents in alliance with the associations			at least 1	White paper with ISDA, DSSC - on sector data spaces?

Table 2 DEPLOYTOUR WP6 KPI

3.4.2 Reporting tools for partners

Monitoring and evaluating is a continuous process that is carried out during the entire lifespan of the project.

Partners will have to report on their dissemination and communication activities on a monthly basis. Feedback is collected from the partners using a shared Excel file available in the common repository:

- Tab 1.1: External Events partners attend
- Tab 1.2: Internal Events partners organised under DEPLOYTOUR
- Tab 2.1: Social Media Monitoring
- Tab 2.2 Media Exposure
- Tab 2.3 Partner Dissemination
- Tab 3.1 DEPLOYTOUR Newsletter

All the monitoring procedures are detailed in the communication guidelines, and available for the partners.

Complete this tab with details about social media posts from your company's LinkedIn, Twitter (X), Facebook, and YouTube pages.

Partners	Related Activity	If not related to an activity, please specify	Social Media Platform	Date of posting	Link	New post or Repost	Impressions	Reactions	Repost
	Kick Off Meeting		LinkedIn			New Post			

Figure 21 WP6 Communication & Dissemination Monitoring Tool

3.4.3 Project website analytics

To monitor the performance of the DEPLOYTOUR website, Google Analytics is being used. This tool provides valuable insights about user behaviour, including:

- Number of users and their engagement levels
- Geographic location of website visitors
- Most popular content and user interactions
- Traffic sources and acquisition channels

By analysing this data, informed decisions can be taken to enhance the website's user experience and overall effectiveness. However, because there's only a landing page with little information, the tool has just begun giving information about visitors. Visitors come mainly from

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direct traffic, which means they are typing the DEPLOYTOUR URL directly into their browser's address bar.

Figure 22 DEPLOYTOUR'S landing traffic sources as from November 19th

3.4.4 Social media analytics

A tool is being tested to aggregate analytics from the three social media platforms. This tool measures post-performance, tracks mentions of DEPLOYTOUR, and manages interactions across these platforms.

LinkedIn

Through LinkedIn, we can get detailed metrics on the performance of our posts, including reach, engagement, impressions and number of clicks. In addition, the platform provides access to how many times the post has been shared, followers gained, video views and interaction rate.

Youtube

YouTube provides an overview of the channel and video performance. Key metrics include views and click-through rates. At the video level, analytics provide information on reach, how the audience discovered the video, as well as impressions and search terms.

X (former Twitter)

As analytics from X are not free anymore, the tool that will be used will allow us to track impressions, engagement and engagement rate.

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4 Networking and Synergies

DEPLOYTOUR will actively engage with its external ecosystem to foster relationships and synergies. WP6 and WP5 will collaborate closely, as their complementary roles focus on identifying and leveraging connections with relevant initiatives and projects, such as the Data Spaces Support Centre (DSSC), SIMPL middleware, and other EU data spaces aligned with DEPLOYTOUR’s use cases. Through these engagements, the project aims to build a robust ecosystem of stakeholders.

The initial list of initiatives is not exhaustive and may expand throughout the project to meet its evolving needs. To facilitate effective collaboration with the initiatives mentioned above, the following instruments and methods will be employed:

- **Active Monitoring:** Ongoing observation of activities and outcomes from data space initiatives such as DSSC, IDSA, and GAIA-X. Partners who are members of these organizations will help maintain strong communication channels.
- **Cross-Communication Channels:** Mutual promotion between DEPLOYTOUR and related initiatives will be established. This includes reciprocal website references, highlighting relationships, and mutual following/tagging on social media to amplify the visibility of news, publications, and events.
- **Joint Events and Publications:** Collaborating on co-located sessions at common events or organizing joint events will enhance the impact across shared communities. This approach maximizes resource efficiency.

To support engagement with these initiatives, the following steps are outlined:

1. **Initial Contacts:** Representatives from DSSC, FiWARE, IDSA, and GAIA-X will be invited to participate in DEPLOYTOUR major events. For example, with the support of AnySolution, a representative from each of these organizations presented their initiatives and actions related to data and tourism during the Kick-off Meeting.
2. **Alignment of Timelines:** Synchronizing plans with the schedules of involved initiatives, considering their working plans.
3. **Event and Publication Calendar:** Developing a shared calendar to schedule joint and common events while coordinating publication deadlines. This helps avoid overlaps, improves resource planning, and maximizes outreach to shared target audiences.
4. **Action Tracking:** Maintaining a comprehensive dashboard to record actions, meetings, and collaborations for monitoring and reporting purposes.

By implementing these strategies, DEPLOYTOUR aims to enhance its influence, foster innovation, and ensure efficient collaboration with key stakeholders in the tourism data space ecosystem.

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5 Conclusion

The scope of this deliverable provides the strategic framework for DEPLOYTOUR dissemination and communication activities in compliance with the objectives and requirements provided by the European Commission, including the proposed activities and tools that will be used during this project to maximise visibility and stakeholder engagement, helping to ensure successful implementation and exploitation of the European Tourism Data Space.

Focusing on the methodology, target audience, and expected outcomes ensures that DEPLOYTOUR's objectives are communicated clearly among the relevant stakeholders in a manner that optimizes its impact on wider digital transition and sustainable tourism within Europe. The structured monitoring and evaluation processes strongly provide for tracking progress against those key objectives and continuous alignment to the goals, and thus the adaptation of the Communication-Dissemination plan in case of need.

The insights and outcomes of DEPLOYTOUR will be crucial throughout in shaping the governance and technical frameworks for data sharing at different levels in the tourism sector. The planned communication-dissemination actions allow proper documentation, sharing, and scaling up of the results, thereby reinforcing this contribution to the European digital ecosystem.

This action aligns with the strategic priorities of the European Commission, such as the Transition Pathway for Tourism, with key topics including Topic 9 (data-driven tourism services) and Topic 14 (technical implementation for the tourism data space).

This deliverable provides the basic structure to be followed and reported in the subsequent Deliverable 6.2. The latter report will be dedicated to dissemination, communication, and exploitation activity reporting after one year of DEPLOYTOUR activities.

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